

An All-Colloidal and Eco-Friendly Quantum-Dot Laser

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Abstract:

Colloidal zinc-chalcogenide quantum dots (QDs) are emerging as the promising heavy-metal-free light-emitters, however, the development of light amplification and lasing therein remains challenging. Here, corroborated by comprehensive in-situ and transient spectroscopy, we unravel that the ultrafast photooxidization-induced trapping process (~ 2 ps) and the sub-bandgap photoinduced absorption under intense excitation are the main hindrances to light amplification in ZnSeTe QDs. Upon tackling the hurdle by heterostructure engineering, we demonstrate that the ZnSeTe QDs exhibit intrinsically superior gain performance, including the high gain cross-section ($5.6 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$), long gain lifetime (615 ps), low pump threshold ($\sim 25.9 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$) and high fatigue resistance. On this basis, we design a microfluidic channel to mass-produce the micellar cavities whose surfaces are treated to combine with the ZnSeTe QDs. The active QD-micelle hybrids show state-of-the-art lasing performance and allow the fiber-based micro-manipulation toward the single-mode lasers. Our findings not only provide essential knowledge on the gain physics in ZnSeTe QDs, but also open a new avenue to develop high-performance eco-friendly lasers.

1. Introduction

The development of solution-processable amplifiers and lasers holds great promise to revolutionize the modern optoelectronic devices thanks to the mechanical flexibility, scalability, and comparability with on-chip integration.^[1-2] Colloidal quantum dots (QDs) have been recognized as the desirable candidates to this end, which feature the high photoluminescence quantum yield (PLQY), band gap tunability and chemical flexibility.^[1-7] The past decade has witnessed the significant progress made in the establishment of QD lasers, including the current-injected stimulated emission diode and continuous-wave monolithic lasing.^[8-9] However, all of these achievements are founded on the heavy-metal-contained QDs (e.g., CdSe), which may have the risks to the human kidneys and nervous systems, thus limiting their wide applications in daily life.^[10] A plenty of eco-friendly QDs have been explored as the alternative gain media, such as InP, AgInS₂ and CuInS₂, while none of them can fulfil the criteria of low pump threshold, large gain coefficient and high fatigue resistance that are comparable to those of the CdSe QDs,^[11-15] due to the intrinsically ill-suited electronic structures, non-stoichiometric trapping states and the dominant sub-bandgap transitions.

Recently, the ternary ZnSeTe alloy QDs are emerging as the desirable heavy-metal-free light-emitting materials. Our group and others have reported that the high-quality ZnSeTe QDs with PLQY of up to ~90% can be obtained by controlling the activity of precursors and cooling processes.^[16-18] Moreover, the emission wavelength can be finely tuned by adjusting the Te-to-Se ratio to cover the entire blue

to yellow regime. Last but not least, the II–VI zinc chalcogenides (ZnX, X=Te, Se and S) theoretically possess similar band structure to that of CdSe,^[5, 19-20] including the p-like valence and s-like conduction band (Figure 1a). Taking all these together, we reason that the ZnSeTe QDs could exhibit auspicious gain properties for coherent light applications. However, until now, only the optical gain from the solution of ZnSeTe well-in-dot heterostructure and the nondeterministic lasing signature have been reported, while the direct observation of emission amplification has not yet been achieved from ZnSeTe QDs.^[21] This indicates that certain hidden mechanisms governing the optical gain or lasing therein remain to be unraveled. In this regard, it is imperative to clarify what happens under the severe operation conditions, including the harsh pumping criteria and high carrier densities, and, on that basis, the high-performance eco-friendly QD lasers could be possibly constructed.

In the current study, we undertook mechanistic studies to reveal that the ultrafast photooxidation-induced trapping process (~2 ps) and the sub-bandgap photoinduced absorption under intense excitation are the main hindrances to light amplification in ZnSeTe QDs by comprehensive in-situ optical spectroscopy. Upon heterostructure regulation to block the photochemical reaction, the amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) with a low pump threshold (~25.9 $\mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$) and high robustness is achieved from ZnSeTe QDs for the first time. The transient absorption characterization further unravels a high gain cross-section of $5.6 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$, large material gain coefficient of 1400 cm^{-1} and long gain lifetime of 615 ps of ZnSeTe QDs, which compete well with those of CdSe counterparts. Finally, we design a microfluidic channel to produce the

micellar cavities and the surfaces are functionalized to combine with the newly-engineered ZnSeTe QDs. This method not only renders the monodisperse QD-micelle hybrids with smooth surfaces, but also allows the on-demand switching on and off for scalable and reproducible fabrication. The active QD-micelles show excellent lasing performance and allow the fiber-based micro-manipulation, such that the laser modulation and single-mode lasing are enabled. The findings clarify that the nascent nontoxic QDs are competent for substituting the heavy-metal-containing QDs as the eligible laser media, which could provide new possibilities in photonics and optoelectronics.

2. Results and Discussion

The tentative light amplification experiments were performed on the conventional double-shelled ZnSeTe/ZnSe/ZnS QDs which are fabricated following the previous reports (see experimental section in Supporting Information for details).^[16, 18] These ZnSeTe QDs show moderate PLQY of ~75% and relatively long Auger recombination lifetime of ~340 ps (Figure S1). The ASE characterization is performed using a femtosecond laser with wavelength of 400 nm, pulse duration of ~100 fs and repetition rate of 1 kHz (see experimental section in Supporting Information for details). It is found that PL quenching occurs when the excitation intensity reaches above $21.2 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$ and no sign of ASE build-up is observed (Figure S2). As for the CdSe-based QDs, the ultrafast (tens of ps) Auger loss has been regarded as the main hindrance against ASE and, hence, the methods to suppress Auger process are adopted to develop high-performance QD lasers.^[8, 22-25] These

observations indicate that different mechanisms are involved in limiting ASE of the eco-friendly ZnSeTe QDs. In contrast to the Cd-based QDs, the Zn-QDs are more prone to oxidation due to the numerous active zinc atoms uncoordinated on the surfaces,^[10, 20] thus, one possibility of the PL quenching and absence of ASE may be induced by the O₂-related photochemical effect in ZnSeTe QDs. To verify the assumption, the in-situ PL measurements under varied atmospheres are performed (see inset of Figure 1b and experimental section in Supporting Information for details). It is found that under the oxygen condition, the drop in the PL intensity under high excitation intensities is observed again (Figure 1b), and it occurs under even lower pump fluence and of greater magnitude than that in air (Figure S2b). In contrast, the PL under Ar atmosphere shows a rather different behavior, where the low-energy side of PL spectrum becomes asymmetric as the pump intensity reaches $\sim 24.9 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$ (Figure 1c). Moreover, a tiny but observable peak appears when the pump intensity increases to $\sim 30.0 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$, which matches the characteristics of ASE at the initial stage.^[26-27] However, with the further increase of pump fluence, the PL intensity drops and the narrow peak disappears. Similar behavior is also observed under N₂ atmosphere (Figure S3). These observations suggest that oxygen brings a considerable impact on the build-up of ASE in ZnSeTe QDs.

To understand how the oxygen affects the gain behaviors, the transient absorption (TA) spectroscopy with time resolution of ~ 100 fs is performed (see experimental section in Supporting Information). Figure 1d shows the typical pseudo-color TA map of the ZnSeTe QDs under O₂ atmosphere and low carrier

density of $\langle N_0 \rangle \sim 0.18$ (see the calculation of average electron-hole pairs per QD $\langle N_0 \rangle$ in experimental section and Figure S4 in Supporting Information). The TA spectra are dominated by the long-lived photobleaching (PB) signals owing to the state-filling of the band-edge state. However, with the increase of carrier density, a broadband photoinduced absorption (PA) feature arises below the band gap (Figure 1e), which covers the potential gain spectra and significantly deteriorate the gain performances (Figure S5). In general, such PA signals arise from the carrier trapping by the permanent photochemical reaction in the QDs or the thermal effect at high carrier density.^[28-29] Note that such PA feature persists once it appears, suggesting that it originates from the permanent photochemical reaction in the QDs. Moreover, we compare the kinetics of the PB signal before and after the high-intensity irradiation (inset of Figure 1e). It is found that the curve after the intense photoexcitation shows an additional ultrafast decay process (~ 2 ps) arising from the photochemical-related carrier trapping. In stark contrast, the PA signal is almost absent when the sample is sealed in an oxygen-free environment (Figure S6a). Meanwhile, the ultrafast decay process of ~ 2 ps does not appear after the photoexcitation (Figure S6b). These behaviors demonstrate that O_2 would induce strong excited-state absorption and ultrafast nonradiative recombination in ZnSeTe QDs to compromise the optical gain.

In principle, the photoexcited carriers in ZnSeTe core readily leak out on the surface to contact with O_2 and induce a series of reactions (see the schematic in Figure 2a), including:

For the widely-used double-shelled ZnSeTe QDs, the total thickness of the epitaxial shells is typically thin (<2.10 nm, see Figure S7a-b).^[16, 30] Due to the anisotropic shelling process, the thin shell usually cannot fully cover the core.^[31] Under intense excitation, the surging carrier density would boost the transfer of photogenerated electrons to oxygen due to the incomplete surface coverage and accelerate the photo-oxidation process, which de-activates the QDs. In order to investigate the effect of laser excitation on the traditional thin-shelled ZnSeTe QDs, the X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was performed. Figure S8a depicts the Se(3d) XPS spectrum of the QD film kept in the atmosphere, which only manifests the signature of Se²⁻. As for the QD film after laser irradiation under atmosphere (excitation intensity: ~39.1 μJ cm⁻², excitation duration: 5 min), a new feature of Se(3d) is revealed (Figure S8b). This peak corresponds to the (SeO_x)²⁻ species,^[32] which suggests that the shielding of the thin shell was invalid and the surface photo-oxidation occurred. Therefore, the thick and uniform shells are desired to alleviate the electron migration and impede the photocorrosion. However, the simple elongation of shell growth time to form the thick shells in ZnSeTe QDs typically gives rise to the inhomogeneous shelling (Figure S7c) and hence inefficient surface passivation. This is attributed to the anisotropic shelling process, where the precursors accumulate in large quantities on the facets with lowest surface energy when the

precursors are injected fast and continuously (see the schematic in Figure 2b).^[5, 10] Furthermore, considering the band alignment of ZnSeTe/ZnSe/ZnS QDs, the electron in the conduction band could be facile to approach the QD surface (Figure 2a). Hence, a new intermediate barrier layer of ZnSeS is applied to construct stepwise energetic potentials that restrict the electron migration. Here, following the previous route to grow thick and uniform shells in QDs,^[5, 33] we inject the precursors for shell growth dropwise at a sufficiently slow rate (2 mL/h for Se-TOP or S-TOP and 4 mL/h for Zn(OA)₂) with the aid of a syringe pump under stirring (see the schematic in Figure 2b and experimental section in Supporting Information for details). As shown in Figure 2c-e, during the slow shelling process, the sizes increase from 7.14 nm of ZnSeTe/ZnSe QDs to 10.01 nm of ZnSeTe/ZnSe/ZnSeS QDs and 11.90 nm of the final ZnSeTe/ZnSe/ZnSeS/ZnS QDs (slow-shelled QDs for abbreviation), corresponding to the formation of the thick ZnSeS (~1.44 nm) and ZnS (~0.95 nm) shells. Furthermore, to ensure the long-term colloidal stability, the surface ligand of the slow-shelled QDs is exchanged by the 1-octanethiol (OT) ligands with a much stronger binding energy (see experimental section in Supporting Information for details). The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the slow-shelled QDs indicate typical zinc blende crystal structure (Figure 2f). The PL decay of the slow-shelled QDs shows a single exponential curve with a long lifetime of ~29.2 ns (Figure 2g), indicating the nearly absence of trap-related nonradiative recombination. Notably, the slow-shelled QDs show high PLQY of 95%, and exhibit a great suppression of the oxidation-induced PA signal and the ultrafast trapping process, suggesting that the

elimination of the nonradiative loss channels (Figure S9). These fundamental photophysical characterizations indicate the high-quality of our slow-shelled QDs.

To explore the ASE from the slow-shelled QDs, the close-packed film is excited by the stripe pumping installation. Figure 3a shows the PL evolution of the QD film with varied pump fluences. Under low excitation intensity ($\sim 2.4 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$), a broad spontaneous emission spectrum with full-width of half maximum (FWHM) of 21.1 nm is observed at 455 nm. With the increase of pump intensity above $\sim 26.4 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$, a narrow emission peak at the longer wavelength side of 460 nm appears, indicating the achievement of ASE. The plot of the integrated emission intensity as a function of pump intensity (inset of Figure 3a) exhibits an ASE threshold of $\sim 25.9 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$, corresponding to $\langle N_0 \rangle = 1.5$.^[34-35] This value is relatively low compared to those of the QDs in blue spectral range.^[28, 35-38] The ASE may originate from the bi-excitonic radiative recombination owing to the threshold carrier density of $\langle N_0 \rangle = 1.5$. More experiments are required to clarify the ASE mechanism in the future. The ASE thresholds from different close-packed films are further measured (Figure S10), and they remain in a similar level of $< \sim 30.0 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$, demonstrating that the low-threshold ASE performance is not dictated by the qualities of the prepared films. Moreover, the effect of ZnSeS/ZnS shell thickness on ASE threshold is assessed. The threshold tends to rise as the shells continue to grow (Figure S11a), perhaps due to the increase of defect states induced by interfacial strain.^[5] The ASE stability is measured under the ambient conditions. It is seen that the ASE maintains a stable output intensity against pump pulses up to $\sim 3.0 \times 10^6$ (corresponding to ~ 50 min, Figure 3b).

The inset in Figure 3b presents the corresponding ASE spectra under different pump durations, which shows only a slight decrease of intensity after long-time laser irradiation. These results indicate the success in overcoming the photochemical reaction in our slow-shelled QDs under high pump fluences. Notably, by fine-tuning the molar ratio of Te, the ASE emission can be tuned from 450 nm to 480 nm to cover the entire blue regime (Figure 3c). As more Te is introduced, the ASE threshold shows an overall upward trend (Figure S11b). Considering the difference in lattice constants between ZnTe (6.101 Å) and ZnSe (5.668 Å),^[16] the trend may be due to the more defects induced by lattice mismatch between the Te-rich core and the shell. The first-principles calculation can well reproduce the bandgap change upon different Te alloying as shown in Figure S12.

Furthermore, the TA spectroscopy is utilized to elucidate the gain dynamics of the slow-shelled QDs. The optical gain g obtained by the TA technique is given by a negative nonlinear absorbance $\alpha = \alpha_0 + \Delta\alpha < 0$, where α_0 is the steady-state absorbance and $\Delta\alpha$ is the pump-induced absorption change. Figure 3d plots the corresponding nonlinear absorption spectra as a function of carrier density. The net gain is revealed to develop at wavelength of 450-470 nm, which is consistent with the ASE results. Figure 3e displays the pseudo-color net gain map of the slow-shelled QDs. It is seen that the gain builds up within a sub-picosecond timescale thanks to the ultrafast hot carrier cooling, which ensures the effective carrier relaxation to the band-edge states for population inversion. The gain lifetime is derived to be as long as

615 ps, which is ascribed to the slow Auger recombination and suppressed trapping processes. Moreover, the gain cross-section of the QDs ($\sigma_{\langle N_0 \rangle}$) can be extracted by:

$$\sigma_{\langle N_0 \rangle}(\lambda) = -\frac{\alpha(\lambda)}{\alpha_0(400 \text{ nm})} \alpha_0(400 \text{ nm}) \quad (5)$$

where $\alpha_0(400 \text{ nm})$ is the absorption cross-section at the 400 nm ($3 \times 10^{-14} \text{ cm}^2$, Figure S4). The evolution of the gain cross-section as a function of the carrier density $\langle N_0 \rangle$ is shown in Figure 3f, which represents a phenomenological fitting of $\sigma_{\langle N_0 \rangle} = A(1 - e^{-\frac{\langle N_0 \rangle}{B}})$.^[39] In this case, the saturated gain cross-section ($\sigma_{\langle N_0 \rangle \rightarrow \infty}$) of the ZnSeTe QDs is determined to be up to $5.6 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$. Accordingly, the material gain coefficient reaches as high as $\sim 1400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (see the calculation of gain coefficient in experimental section of Supporting Information). Besides, the modal gain of the slow-shelled QD film is also measured by the variable-stripe-length (VSL) method (Figure S13), demonstrating a gain of $\sim 1099 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ that is slightly lower than the material gain by TA measurement. Both of them compete well with those of the Cd-containing QDs,^[1, 39-40] indicative of the high density of states available for ASE in ZnSeTe QDs.

To practically feed the slow-shelled QDs with high-quality resonators, a microfluidic configuration is designed to produce micellar cavities by batch self-assembly (see details in experimental section of Supporting Information). As the dispersed phase (polystyrene (PS)/trichloromethane (TCM)) and the continuous phase fluid (sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS)/glycerin) converge in the microfluidic channel, the dispersed fluid is stretched and breaks (see Figure 4a for the schematic procedures). As a result, the emulsion droplet is generated under the surface

destabilization condition, and this droplet is maintained by balancing the viscous force and interfacial tension. Upon the formation of a droplet, the instantaneous increase in upstream pressure drives the creation of the next one.^[41] Figure 4b shows the large-scale PS micelles produced in one batch, which possess smooth surfaces and circular boundaries. Nevertheless, it is noted that the direct coating of the slow-shelled QDs on the micelle cavities results in non-uniform distribution and even cracks (Figure 4c and Figure S14a), which will induce undesirable scattering losses. This is because that the phenyl PS matrix has no functional groups and basically relies on the π - π interaction to bind with π -conjugated molecules. However, none of the commonly used ligands for zinc-chalcogenide QDs (e.g., alkylamines, alkyl thiols and alkyl phosphines) possesses a delocalized π -conjugated system.^[10, 42] On this basis, the surface functionalization of the PS micelles is applied with C₂H₇NS molecules (see experimental section in Supporting Information for details), such that the sulfhydryl (-SH) functional groups can form a strong covalent bond with the OT ligands. It is found that the treated ZnSeTe-micelles show a smooth surface (Figure 4d and Figure S14b), and the energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS) mapping (Figure 4e-g) demonstrates the uniform distribution of QDs on the micelle surface.

To investigate the lasing performance of the slow-shelled QD-micelle hybrids, a home-built micro-PL system is adopted (see experimental section in Supporting Information for details). Figure 4h shows the PL spectra from an individual QD-micelle under varied excitation fluences. The broad spontaneous emission is observed at low pump intensities ($< \sim 18.7 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$). As the pump intensity increases

to $\sim 31.2 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$, the sharp and evenly spaced lasing peaks appear. The plot of the integrated PL intensity as a function of pump fluence reveals a low threshold of $\sim 20.9 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$ (inset of Figure 4h). The Q-factor is derived to be as high as ~ 3550 (Figure S15) based on the formula $Q = \lambda/\delta\lambda$, where λ and $\delta\lambda$ is the center wavelength and the FWHM of the lasing peak, respectively.^[27] By tentatively fitting the sharp peaks based on the whispering gallery mode (WGM) theory,^[27] the lasing spikes can be well assigned by mode numbers from 228 to 232 (Figure S16), indicating the WGM lasing mechanism in the system. Moreover, the electric field distribution of the micellar laser in X-Y and Y-Z planes (see coordinate in Figure S17) is calculated using the finite element method (Figure 4i-j). The zoomed-in local area on the right side reveals that the electric field lie mainly in the inner part of the PS micelle, which indicates that only a small portion of energy leaks out through the evanescent wave, which guarantees the high Q-factor of the QD-micelle laser.

Furthermore, the micelle hybrid is robust and compatible with the micro-manipulation technique, accordingly, the single mode lasing can be realized via mode competition by positioning two micelles adjacently. As a demonstration, one micelle with a diameter of $20 \mu\text{m}$ is put adjacent to another with a diameter of $23 \mu\text{m}$ (inset of Figure 4k). The lasing spectra from the single (Figure S18) and coupled cavities are (Figure 4k) radically different, where the single mode lasing is clearly observed for the latter. This is attributed to that when the dual-coupled system is excited simultaneously, one of the cavities performs as a mode filter for the other, as manifested by the theoretical calculation.^[43] The simulation of the electric field

distribution of the coupled system is shown in Figure 4l, where both microcavities are in the co-frequency resonance in the non-Hermitian system. In this case, only a single eigenmode satisfying the resonance conditions within the gain spectrum is strengthened and the rest are suppressed, thereby leading to the development of single mode lasing.^[43]

3. Conclusion

The high-performance eco-friendly and all-colloidal laser is developed from ZnSeTe QDs leveraging on the exceptional gain property and microfluidic manufacturing technique. We disclose that, rather than Auger limitation for the traditional CdSe-based QDs, the photooxidization process and the sub-bandgap photoinduced absorption are the culprit for hindering ASE in ZnSeTe QDs. Upon tackling the hurdles, we show that the ZnSeTe QDs exhibit intrinsically superior gain performance. These results represent significant progress toward high-performance eco-friendly lasers from solution-processable QDs.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in the Supporting Information of this article.

Keywords

Colloidal quantum dots, eco-friendly laser, amplified spontaneous emission, microfluidics, single-mode laser

Figure 1. a) Simplified electronic structure of CdSe (left) and ZnSe (right). PL spectra from ZnSeTe/ZnSe/ZnS QD film under b) O_2 atmosphere and c) Ar atmosphere; inset of b) schematizes the in-situ PL system. d) Pseudocolor TA image of the ZnSeTe/ZnSe/ZnS QDs at $\langle N_0 \rangle \sim 0.18$. e) TA spectra as a function of carrier density from 0.18 to 5.22; the inset shows the PB kinetics before and after the laser irradiation.

Figure 2. a) Illustration of the energy levels of ZnSeTe/ZnSe/ZnS QDs and the process that the photoexcited electron transfers to the surface-adsorbed oxygen. b) Illustration of heterostructure formation by fast injection shelling and slow injection shelling methods. TEM images of c) ZnSeTe/ZnSe, d) ZnSeTe/ZnSe/ZnSeS and e) ZnSeTe/ZnSe/ZnSeS/ZnS QDs synthesized through slow injection shelling method. f) XRD pattern of slow-shelled QDs. g) Fluorescence lifetime of slow-shelled QDs.

Figure 3. a) PL spectra of slow-shelled QD film under varied pump fluences; the inset presents the emission intensity of QD film as a function of pump intensity. b) The ASE intensity of QD film under the constant excitation intensity of $\sim 41.6 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$; the inset shows the ASE spectra at the initiation and end of the excitation. c) Normalized ASE spectra at different Te/Se molar ratio. d) Nonlinear absorption spectra of the QDs at 1 ps for different carrier densities; inset: zoom on the band-edge part, showing the transition from absorption to net gain. e) Net gain map of the QDs at carrier density of $\langle N_0 \rangle \sim 6.35$. f) Gain cross-section of the QDs as a function of $\langle N_0 \rangle$.

Figure 4. a) Schematic diagram of the fabrication of monodisperse micelles by a microfluidic channel. b) Optical image of the large-scale monodisperse micelles; scale bar: 20 μm . c-d) Optical microscopic images of individual QD-micelle with directly coated QDs and that after surface functionalization; scale bar: 10 μm . e-g) Elemental mappings showing the distribution of the chemical elements; scale bar: 5 μm . h) Lasing spectra of an individual micelle; the insets show the photograph of a QD-micelle (scale bar: 20 μm) and the emission intensity as a function of pump intensity. i-j) Electric field distributions in X-Y and Z-Y planes of a QD-micelle cavity. k) Lasing spectra of coupled micelles; the insets show the photograph of coupled micelles (scale bar: 20 μm) and the emission intensity as a function of pump intensity. (l) Electric field distribution in X-Y plane of coupled cavities.

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The table of contents entry:

The eco-friendly and all-colloidal microlaser is developed from the ZnSeTe QDs. We disclose that the photooxidization process and the photoinduced absorption are the main hindrances to the light amplification in ZnSeTe QDs. Upon heterostructure regulation, the low-threshold and robust amplified spontaneous emission is achieved from ZnSeTe QDs for the first time. On that basis, a high-performance laser is constructed.

Table of Content Graphic:

